

CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING AND PRIVACY-PRESERVING TECHNOLOGIES FOR 6G

D4.1 REQUIREMENTS AND ARCHITECTURE FOR CONFIDENTIAL NETWORKING

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D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of Acronyms and Abbreviations	7
List of Figures	9
List of Tables	10
Executive Summary	11
1 Introduction.....	12
1.1 Scope	12
1.2 Overview of Confidential Networking.....	13
1.3 Structure	15
2 Framework And Standard For Capturing Requirements	16
2.1 Introduction To Requirements Engineering.....	16
2.2 Volere Template Field description	17
2.3 IETF RFC 2119.....	19
2.4 Requirements Documenting Template	20
3 Generic Requirements for Confidential Networking	21
3.1 Threat Analysis.....	21
3.2 Generic Requirements	23
3.2.1 Functional Requirements	23
3.2.2 Non-functional Requirements	27
4 Use Case Requirements	31
4.1 Use Case 1: Predictive Maintenance for Airline Consortium.....	31
4.1.1 Requirements Analysis	32
4.2 Use Case 2: Privacy-preserving Confidential Computing Platform	34
4.2.1 Requirements Analysis	35
4.3 Use Case 3: Intelligent Connected Vehicles	37

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

4.3.1	Requirements Analysis	38
5	Architecture Blueprints	45
5.1	High Level Architecture	45
5.2	Confidential Orchestration	46
5.3	DLT-based Data Sharing	48
5.4	Federated AI/ML.....	52
5.4.1	FL Computing	52
5.4.2	FL Orchestration	54
5.4.3	Federated Learning Security/ Privacy	57
5.5	Post-quantum TLS	61
6	Conclusion	66
	References.....	67

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
4G/5G/6G	<i>The 4th, 5th, 6th Generation of Cellular Networks</i>
ADL	<i>Activities of Daily Living</i>
AI	<i>Artificial Intelligence</i>
API	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
CA-BCFL	<i>Centralized Aggregated Blockchain Federated Learning</i>
CoCo	<i>Confidential Containers Project</i>
DIDs	<i>Decentralized Identifiers</i>
DLT	<i>Distributed Ledger Technology</i>
DP	<i>Differential Privacy</i>
FD-BCFL	<i>Fully Decentralized Blockchain Federated Learning</i>
FHE	<i>Fully Homomorphic Encryption</i>
FL	<i>Federated Learning</i>
FLaaS	<i>Federated Learning as a Service</i>
FPGA	<i>Field Programmable Gate Arrays</i>
FR	<i>Functional Requirement</i>
GDPR	<i>General Data Protection Regulation</i>
HE	<i>Homomorphic Encryption</i>
HHE	<i>Hybrid Homomorphic Encryption</i>
IoT	<i>Internet of Things</i>
SGX	<i>Software Guard Extensions</i>
TDX	<i>Trust Domain Extensions</i>
KEM	<i>Key Encapsulation Mechanism</i>
MEC	<i>Multi-Access Edge Computing</i>
ML	<i>Machine Learning</i>

MPC	<i>Multi-Party Computation</i>
NF	<i>Non-functional Requirement</i>
OEMs	<i>Original Equipment Manufacturer</i>
O-RAN	<i>Open Radio Access Network</i>
OTA	<i>Over The Air</i>
PETs	<i>Privacy-preserving Technologies</i>
PKE	<i>Public Key Encryption</i>
PQC	<i>Post-quantum Cryptography</i>
RR	<i>Regulatory Requirement</i>
SEV	<i>Secure Memory Encryption</i>
SDR	<i>Software Defined Radio</i>
SIM	<i>Subscriber Identity Module</i>
SoCs	<i>System on Chips</i>
SR	<i>Security Requirement</i>
TCP	<i>Transmission Control Protocol</i>
TEEs	<i>Trusted Execution Environments</i>
TLS	<i>Transport Layer Security</i>
UCD	<i>University College Dublin</i>
V2I	<i>Vehicle to Infrastructure</i>
VC	<i>Verifiable Credentials</i>
VM	<i>Virtual Machine</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>
XAI	<i>Explainable Artificial Intelligence</i>
ZKP	<i>Zero Knowledge Proof</i>

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: Overview of Confidential Networking.....	12
Figure 2: High Level Architecture for Secure and Confidential Networking	45
Figure 3: Initial Architectural Consideration of Components Relevant for Confidential Orchestration.....	47
Figure 4: Secure and Traceable Data Sharing based on DLT.....	50
Figure 5: Overview of FL Computing	52
Figure 6: Server Diagram in FL Computing	53
Figure 7: Party Node Diagram in FL Computing	54
Figure 8: FLaaS High Level Overview in [4].....	55
Figure 9: FLaaS Architecture in [4]	56
Figure 10: Blockchain based Poisoning Defence Strategy for FL.....	58
Figure 11: Overview of the XAI-enabled FL Poisoning Defence Strategy.....	59
Figure 12: FL Security Testbed.....	60
Figure 13: Post-quantum TLS Security Protocol Design	62

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Volere Template.....	17
Table 2: Requirements Documenting Template	20
Table 3:Threat analysis of Confidential Networking.....	21
Table 4: Functional Requirements of Confidential Networking.....	24
Table 5: Non-functional Requirements of Confidential Networking	27
Table 6: Functional Requirements of Predictive Maintenance for Airline Consortium Using Blockchain-based Data Sharing Platform and Federated AI/ML Orchestration (UC1)	32
Table 7: Non-functional Requirements of Predictive Maintenance for Airline Consortium Using Blockchain-based Data Sharing Platform and Federated AI/ML Orchestration (UC1)	33
Table 8: Functional Requirements of Privacy-preserving Confidential Computing Platform (UC2)	35
Table 9: Non-functional Requirements of Privacy-preserving Confidential Computing Platform (UC2).....	36
Table 10: Functional Requirements of Intelligent Connected Vehicles (UC3)	38
Table 11: Non-functional Requirements of Intelligent Connected Vehicles (UC3).....	42

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current document constitutes the first version of the CONFIDENTIAL6G Requirements and architecture blueprint for confidential networking. It is meant to serve as a reference on necessary requirements for secure and confidential networking, data sharing and service and computation orchestration, leveraging on federated AI/ML to increase privacy-preserving by enabling scenarios in which data is kept in premise on the edge, while algorithms are brought to the data. Requirements analysed include long-term security, calling for post-quantum solutions, as well as computation power and bandwidth limitations.

It should be noted that as work progresses the requirements and architecture for confidential networking will be updated if and as necessary in the next work package (WP) 4 Deliverables.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 SCOPE

The sixth generation (6G) of cellular networks is expected to provide a reliable, trustworthy, and resilient service with substantial increase of coverage and network heterogeneity. The emerging technologies such as post-quantum cryptography (PQC), artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML) and distributed ledger technology (DLT) are playing a significant role in achieving the 6G objectives. New requirements and architectures for the 6G security and privacy such as authentication, encryption, access control and communication must be redefined to integrate these technologies seamlessly into 6G network.

Figure 1: Overview of Confidential Networking

This document focuses on confidential networking in 6G. The document covers protection of data transmitted over networks with encryption and secure protocols such as Transport Layer Security (TLS) as well as protection of systems enabling distributed network applications to be shared, orchestrated, and operated securely. We provide various requirements and an architecture blueprint for 6G confidential

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

networking that represents a description of what the work on confidential networking within the project is expected to address, in line with the project objectives.

1.2 OVERVIEW OF CONFIDENTIAL NETWORKING

Confidential networking protects the data “in transit” when it is flowing between untrusted public or private networks, as shown in *Figure 1*. It develops the secure, future-proof and quantum-safe orchestration mechanism, aiming to improve the data exchange and sharing security over the cloud-edge continuum, especially for data communication in blockchain, federated AI/ML orchestration and confidential computing scenarios. Confidential networking is a broad research topic involving many problems, which includes but is not limited to:

- Ensure secure data exchange and sharing over the cloud-edge continuum.
- Orchestration mechanism to improve data privacy by improving federated AI/ML in the context of confidential computing.
- Data verification and access control mechanisms leveraging on the modern blockchain network.

Cryptographic enablers are important tools to solve the above problems and achieve the security and privacy requirement in 6G confidential networking. These include:

- **PQC primitives:** they serve as essential enablers when protecting against quantum attackers.
- **Zero knowledge proof (ZKP):** enhances blockchain with anonymity and privacy protection.
- **Fully homomorphic encryption (FHE):** increase the privacy of smart contracts.
- **DLT:** potential for decentralized identifiers (DIDs) and anonymous and verifiable credentials (VC).
- **Trusted execution environments (TEEs):** confidential containers and solutions based on hardware enclaves.

Corresponding to the above research problems, the possible solution designed based on these cryptographic enablers are:

- Post-quantum TLS and other networking protocols implementation.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

- End-to-end encryption, quantum-safe blockchain consensus and blockchain confidentiality implementations.
- Secure data sharing using DLT.
- Confidential containers and federated AI/ML orchestration.

The development of these solutions can not only enhance 6G communication security with PQC, but also enforce data access control and traceability with DLT platform built upon them. The related research has a high impact, and the developed solutions have a variety of applications in many different fields, such as:

- **Industry:** these technologies can be used to protect intellectual property and trade secrets.
- **Research:** These technologies can be used to collaborate on sensitive research projects.
- **Government:** These technologies can be used to protect classified information in such as a public space and general use where 6G will be applied.

The benefits of adopting confidential networking include:

- **Increased data privacy and security:** These technologies can help to protect sensitive data from unauthorized access, even by cloud providers and system administrators.
- **Improved collaboration:** These technologies can make it possible for organizations to collaborate on sensitive data without having to share the data itself.
- **Enhanced research:** These technologies can help researchers to collaborate on sensitive research projects without compromising the privacy of the data.
- **Increased innovation:** These technologies can help organizations to innovate by giving them the confidence to use sensitive data in new ways.

Despite the high potential of confidential networking, it still faces some challenges:

- **Technology:** although the advancement of cryptography research, the existing solutions still have limited capabilities in available operations and performance
- **Massiveness:** 6G network supports various devices such as cloud, Internet of Things (IoT) and edge nodes. Contemporary security solutions for

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

networks are not designed for serving a massive number of connected and high-mobility heterogeneous devices.

- **Complexity:** the variety of devices and the security requirements increase the complexity of confidential networking implementations.
- **Standardization:** owing to the technical difficulties and problem complexity, standardization is still missing.

1.3 STRUCTURE

The structure of this Deliverable is organized as follows: Section 2 introduces the standard and the Volere template [1] for capturing the requirements. Section 3 presents the collected necessary requirements for secure and confidential networking following the requirements engineering approach indicated in Section 2. Section 3 presents the generic requirements for secure and confidential networking. Additional requirements from the three use cases developed in WP5 are presented in Section 4. Section 5 defines the confidential networking architecture, to guarantee secure and confidential edge-cloud communication, control, and orchestration infrastructure in 6G networks, which includes: confidential orchestration, DLT-base data sharing, Federated AI/ML and post-quantum TLS. Section 6 concludes the document with a summary of the key points.

2 FRAMEWORK AND STANDARD FOR CAPTURING REQUIREMENTS

2.1 INTRODUCTION TO REQUIREMENTS ENGINEERING

Requirements Engineering (RE) is a systematic process that encompasses several critical steps to define, analyze, and document the needs and constraints for a system. The goal is to produce a comprehensive set of requirements organized using the Volere template, a widely recognized framework for requirements documentation. The process outlined here provides a structured approach to ensure clarity, consistency, and alignment across all requirements.

This section introduces the key stages of the Requirements Engineering process. The overview of these stages and their objectives:

- **Requirement Collection:** This step involves gathering requirements derived from use cases, which serve as the foundation of this document. It also includes capturing detailed use case descriptions.
- **Requirements Consistency Checking:** This stage addresses potential conflicts or inconsistencies in requirements, particularly when sourced from multiple contributors. Resolving such issues ensures coherence across the requirements set.
- **Requirement Rewriting, Factorization, and Alignment:** Here, duplicate requirements are eliminated, and commonalities are consolidated. The requirements are also rewritten to align with a unified vocabulary, fostering consistency and ease of understanding.
- **Requirement Mapping:** This involves categorizing and associating requirements to different system perspectives:
 - Functional Requirements (FR): Mapped to a Functional View through functional decomposition.
 - Non-Functional Requirements (NF): Mapped to additional system views and perspectives, ensuring a holistic representation of the system.

Through these steps, the Requirements Engineering process lays a robust foundation for subsequent design and development activities, ensuring that the final system aligns with stakeholder expectations and technical feasibility.

2.2 VOLERE TEMPLATE FIELD DESCRIPTION

The Volere template is a comprehensive framework designed to systematically capture, organize, and document requirements. Each field in the template corresponds to a specific aspect of a requirement, ensuring clarity, traceability, and completeness [1],[2]. Below is a detailed description of the key fields in the Volere template. However, only a subset of the Volere template fields (in yellow) has been used in the requirement tables assigned to each use case.

Table 1: Volere Template

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
ID	Each requirement is uniquely identified
Requirement Type	It is easier to write an appropriate fit criterion when the type of requirement is established. The requirement can be generalized into Functional Requirements (FR) and Non-Functional Requirements (NF). In the following specification of requirements the requirement type in the requirement ID.
Description	The description is the intent of the requirement. It is a statement about what the system must fulfil according to the rationale (see further below).
Categories	<p>Technical or non-technical topics covered by the requirement. Could be more than one. An indicative list is provided below</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security • Privacy • Trust • Performance • Scalability • Platform • Machine learning • Networking • Blockchain • Data Reliability • Data Privacy • Data Processing • Data Management • AI/ML Orchestration • Identity Management • Federated Learning

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access Control • Performance Metrics • System Reliability • Management • Interoperability • Usability • Regulatory • Compliance • Societal • Ethics •
Rationale	The rationale is the reason behind the requirement's existence. It explains why the requirement is important and how it contributes to the system's purpose.
Owner/ Source/Req. Name	The owner or originator is the person or organization which raised the requirement in the first instance or the person to whom it can be attributed. The originator's name should be attached to the requirements so that there is a referral point if questions about the requirement arise or if the requirement is rejected. The person who raises the requirement must have the knowledge and authority appropriate for the type of requirement.
Originating Scenario/BC	Identifier (ID) of the originating use case scenario or business case (BC) if relevant.
Fit Criterion	A quantification or measurement to assess to which extent the original requirement has been eventually implemented or taken into account within the system. Can be used as the "Definition-of-Done" in agile development practices.
Priority	The priority of a requirement is the decision on the importance of the requirement's implementation. The priority depends highly on the specific domain of the application. Priority takes values from {high, medium, low} with a decreasing priority level where high, medium, and low mean, respectively, compulsory, recommended, and optional.
Dependencies [optional]	Indicates if the requirement depends on another one. Relations between two or more requirements should be noted and separated by comma(s).
Conflict [optional]	Conflicts between requirements imply that there are contradictions upon system implementation, or one requirement makes the implementation of

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

	another requirement less feasible. Values: default "(none)" or requirement number(s), separated by comma(s).
View	One or several views to which the requirement is related.
Functionality Group	One or several functionality groups in the functional decomposition to which the requirement is related.
Functional Component	One or several components in the functional decomposition to which the requirement is related. These functional components are part of the groups listed in the functionality-group field.
Domain Model	One or several domain-model entities to which the requirement is related.
Perspective	One or several perspectives to which a requirement is related.
System Use-Case	ID of the System Use Case that needs the requirement under consideration.
Comment [optional]	Any comment providing useful information.

2.3 IETF RFC 2119

IETF RFC 2119 is a technical document published by the Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) that establishes a set of standardized keywords and their definitions for use in technical specifications [3]. These keywords help clarify the degree of compliance or obligation associated with specific requirements or recommendations.

The document defines the following keywords and their meanings:

1. **MUST**: Signifies a mandatory requirement. Compliance requires strict adherence to this specification.
2. **MUST NOT**: Indicates a prohibition. Compliance requires strict avoidance of this specification.
3. **REQUIRED**: Equivalent to "MUST."
4. **SHOULD**: Represents a strong recommendation. While not strictly required, it is generally expected that most implementations will comply.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

5. **SHOULD NOT:** Expresses a strong recommendation against a particular action. Although not strictly prohibited, it is expected that most implementations will avoid this.
6. **MAY:** Denotes permission. Implementations have the option to follow or disregard this specification.
7. **OPTIONAL:** Equivalent to "MAY."

Example Usage

- "A compliant server *MUST* implement the TLS protocol." This mandates that TLS is required for compliance.
- "A server *SHOULD* support the HTTP/2 protocol." This indicates that supporting HTTP/2 is recommended but not mandatory.

2.4 REQUIREMENTS DOCUMENTING TEMPLATE

The IETF RFC 2119 standard can be effectively applied within the Volere template. RFC 2119 introduces a set of keywords, such as "MUST," "SHOULD," and "MAY," to indicate different levels of requirement obligations in technical specifications. These keywords are particularly valuable for clearly defining requirements within the VOLERE template, which is structured to facilitate the systematic capture and management of requirements. Integrating RFC 2119 terminology into the Volere template ensures that requirements are precise and standardized. This approach enhances clarity and consistency across project documentation, making it easier to interpret and implement requirements.

A table for documenting requirements using this terminology is provided below:

Table 2: Requirements Documenting Template

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion

3 GENERIC REQUIREMENTS FOR CONFIDENTIAL NETWORKING

3.1 THREAT ANALYSIS

Confidential networking aims to improve the protection of data “in transit” between 6G infrastructures: cloud, devices, and network. The communication protection between these infrastructures will be enhanced with PQC to defend the arising threats with quantum computing power. Besides, data exchange will be enforced leveraging blockchain technologies and secure data access control and traceability platforms built upon them.

Threat analysis for confidential networking involves systematically identifying, evaluating, and prioritizing risks to ensure the security, integrity, and confidentiality of the network and its data. The table below provides a structured overview of key threats to confidential networking, highlighting the specific security properties they violate, their definitions, expected scenarios where such threats may manifest, and the recommended mitigation measures. By categorizing threats in this manner, organizations can better understand the risks to their network's confidentiality, integrity, and availability. This systematic approach ensures targeted and effective measures are implemented to safeguard sensitive information, reduce vulnerabilities, and enhance overall network security.

Table 3:Threat analysis of Confidential Networking

Threat	Property Violated	Definition	Expected scenarios	Measures
Eavesdropping	Confidentiality	Interception of network traffic to extract sensitive data.	Sniffing unencrypted traffic over Wi-Fi or public networks.	Encrypt data (TLS, VPN), secure access points, use strong
Man-in-the-Middle	Confidentiality, Integrity	Attackers insert themselves between two communicating parties.	Fake websites, rogue Wi-Fi hotspots, or DNS spoofing.	Use mutual TLS, certificate pinning, and implement strong endpoint security.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

Practical Quantum Computer	Confidentiality Integrity	A practical quantum computer can break the security of classical cryptography.	Sudden or steady advance on quantum computers make cryptographically relevant quantum computers probable.	Transition to Post-quantum secure cryptography.
DDoS Attacks	Availability	Overloading the network to disrupt services.	Flooding servers with requests or exploiting IoT devices.	Deploy DDoS mitigation tools, use rate-limiting, and scale resources.
Phishing	Confidentiality	Deceiving users into revealing credentials or sensitive data.	Fraudulent emails or links leading to malicious websites.	Train employees, deploy anti-phishing tools, and enforce MFA.
Rogue Access Points	Confidentiality	Fake wireless hotspots to intercept data.	Employees unknowingly connecting to malicious Wi-Fi.	Conduct Wi-Fi scanning, disable auto-connect, and use network segmentation.
Compromised Credentials	Confidentiality, Integrity	Stolen credentials granting unauthorized access.	Credential theft via brute force, phishing, or malware.	Enforce MFA, monitor login anomalies, and use password policies.
Unsecured APIs	Confidentiality, Integrity	Exploitation of APIs to bypass access controls.	Unauthorized data access via vulnerable APIs.	Secure APIs with tokens, rate-limit requests, and conduct regular testing.
Data Exfiltration	Confidentiality	Stealthy transfer of sensitive data out of the network.	Malware or insiders using email or USB drives to extract data.	Use DLP solutions, monitor outbound traffic, and enforce strict policies.
Traffic Analysis	Confidentiality, Anonymity	Monitoring metadata to infer	Passive observation of network traffic.	Implement onion routing, use encrypted tunnels,

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

		communication patterns.		and minimize metadata leaks.
Zero-Day Exploits	Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability	Exploitation of unknown vulnerabilities.	Malware or APT attacks exploiting new vulnerabilities.	Regular patching, threat intelligence, and proactive monitoring.
Information leaking from confidential distributed workloads	Confidentiality, anonymity	Fingerprinting and identifying confidential applications (or their users) in shared infrastructure	Access to VMs or containers by circumventing access control, leaking side-channel information may be used to fingerprint containers	Access / platform / hardware specific controls over who can control side-channels. Differential privacy (noise) to prevent side-channel leaks
Deploying confidential applications to misbehaving infrastructure	Confidentiality, Integrity	Misbehaving infrastructure owner or operator may circumvent all access controls and applications	Malicious access leading to data leakage or tampering of confidential code/data. Attacks include compromised hypervisor, physical and insider.	Remote attestation, platform security posture
Malicious workloads (containers)	Confidentiality, integrity	Malicious containers /VMs in shared infrastructure threaten hosts and other applications	Malicious containers may utilize unpatched vulnerabilities to get out of sandboxes, to escalate privileges	Strong sandboxing over containers, patching
Database Reconstruction	Privacy	Reconstruction attacks infer personal information from statistical results	Published datasets could be analyzed by adversaries and are prone to data leakage.	Obfuscating relations to individuals by means of differential privacy or k-anonymity.

3.2 GENERIC REQUIREMENTS

3.2.1 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 4: Functional Requirements of Confidential Networking

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP4_FR_1	Privacy	Data MUST be kept confidential applying federated learning, so the minimum amount of data is shared and only the weights of the model are shared.	To protect data from unauthorized access and ensure confidentiality	Data is protected using federated learning, whereby the raw data of each client is not shared.
WP4_FR_2	Privacy	Data MUST be kept confidential during transmission and at rest using differential privacy.	To protect data from unauthorized access and ensure confidentiality	Data is protected using local differential privacy, whereby the raw data of each client is not shared.
WP4_FR_3	Machine Learning	The system MUST support training machine learning models on the edge and in the cloud.	To leverage local and cloud resources to optimize and improve results.	Machine learning models such as neural networks must be trained on the cloud and on edge devices, at least in a federated fashion.
WP4_FR_4	Machine Learning	The system SHOULD support a federated system that allows training with large models, to capture large amounts of data.	To be able to make use of large new models such as foundation models and not have problems with large amounts of data.	Foundation models will be used and trained on cloud and edge devices to get the most out of both models and devices.
WP4_FR_5	Privacy	Data MUST be encrypted during transmission and at rest	To protect data from unauthorized access and	Data is encrypted using AES-256 during

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

		using industry-standard encryption protocols.	ensure confidentiality.	transmission and at rest.
WP4_FR_6	Privacy	Personal data SHOULD be anonymized before sharing to protect user privacy.	To comply with privacy regulations and protect user identities.	Personal data is anonymized using a standard anonymization technique.
WP4_FR_7	Trust	A trust framework MUST be established to verify the identity and integrity of all entities involved in data exchange.	To ensure that only trusted entities can participate in data exchange.	A trust framework is implemented and verified through digital certificates.
WP4_FR_8	Networking	The system MUST use secure network protocols (e.g., TLS) for data transmission.	To protect data in transit from interception and tampering.	Data is transmitted using TLS 1.2 or higher.
WP4_FR_9	Machine Learning	The system SHOULD support training machine learning models on the edge and in the cloud.	To leverage local and cloud resources for efficient model training.	Machine learning models can be trained on edge devices and cloud platforms.
WP4_FR_10	Blockchain	The system MUST use blockchain to ensure data integrity and immutability.	To provide a tamper-proof record of all data transactions.	All data transactions are recorded on a blockchain ledger.
WP4_FR_11	Blockchain	The system MUST support smart contracts for automated data sharing agreements.	To automate and enforce data sharing policies.	Smart contracts are used to manage data sharing agreements.
WP4_FR_12	Blockchain	The system MUST implement decentralized identity management using blockchain.	To ensure secure and verifiable identities for all participants.	Decentralized identities are managed and verified using blockchain.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

WP4_FR_1 3	Blockchain	The system MUST use blockchain-based access control for authorization.	To ensure secure and decentralized access control.	Access control policies are enforced using blockchain-based mechanisms.
WP4_FR_1 4	Blockchain	The system MUST use blockchain for decentralized authentication.	To provide secure and verifiable authentication without a central authority.	Authentication is performed using blockchain-based mechanisms.
WP4_FR_1 5	Blockchain	The system MUST ensure user privacy through zero-knowledge proofs (ZKPs) on blockchain.	To protect user privacy while verifying transactions.	User transactions are verified using ZKPs without revealing sensitive information.
WP4_FR_1 6	Management	Deployment and configuration (i.e. orchestration) of confidential workloads SHOULD be automatable.	Automation supports flexibility and resilience and improves cost-efficiency.	Automation features are integrated to orchestration system.
WP4_FR_1 7	Security	Computing infrastructure (host platform and other tenants) MUST be protected from misbehaving confidential workloads.	Implementing the principle of least privileges is necessary to enable third-party infrastructure to approve distributed workloads.	Platform interfaces protected with access control
WP4_FR_1 8	Security	Configuration and integrity of the features enabling confidential orchestration SHOULD be remotely attestable.	Platform health attestation increases workloads providers' trust	Attestation has been integrated to orchestration system.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

			towards available infrastructure.	
WP4_FR_19	Security	Security threats caused by deployment and configuration of confidential workloads MUST be identified and mitigated.	Orchestration may open new threats and attacks (including, communication, physical & side channels). Modelling and mitigating all threats make confidential computing concepts more acceptable.	Detailed security analysis covering orchestration and virtualization approaches done. Risks are mitigated continuously when new threats are found.

3.2.2 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 5: Non-functional Requirements of Confidential Networking

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP4_NF_1	Performance	The system MUST support data processing at the edge to reduce latency and bandwidth usage.	To improve performance and reduce the load on central servers.	Data processing tasks are executed on edge devices, reducing central server load.
WP4_NF_2	Performance	The system MUST support training machine learning models on the edge and in the cloud.	To leverage local and cloud resources to optimize and improve results.	Machine learning models such as neural networks must be trained on the cloud and on edge devices, at least in a federated fashion.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

WP4_NF_3	Scalability	The system SHOULD support a federated system that allows training with large models, to capture large amounts of data.	To be able to make use of large new models such as foundation models and not have problems with large amounts of data.	Foundation models will be used and trained on cloud and edge devices to get the most out of both models and devices.
WP4_NF_4	Performance	The system SHOULD ensure data retrieval and sharing operations are completed within a specified time frame.	To provide a responsive user experience.	Data retrieval and sharing operations complete within a defined timeframe almost all the cases.
WP4_NF_5	Scalability	The system MUST support horizontal scaling to accommodate increasing data volumes and user loads.	To handle growing data and user demands without performance degradation.	The system can add additional nodes to handle increased load without downtime.
WP4_NF_6	Performance	The system MUST ensure low latency for data exchange operations.	To provide real-time data exchange capabilities.	Data exchange operations have an average latency of less than 10 ms.
WP4_NF_7	Interoperability	The system MUST comply with relevant standards (e.g., IETF, IEEE) to ensure interoperability.	To enable seamless integration with other systems and devices.	The system adheres to IETF and IEEE standards for data exchange.
WP4_NF_8	Usability	The system MUST provide a centralized management console for monitoring and administration.	To simplify system management and oversight.	A centralized management console is available for system administrators.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

WP4_NF_9	Regulatory & Compliance	The system MUST comply with relevant regulatory and compliance requirements for data sharing.	The system complies with GDPR, CCPA, PCI DSS, and other relevant regulations.	
WP4_NF_1	Scalability	Confidential computations (code and data) SHOULD be dynamically distributable to allocated computing resources in cloud-edge continuum.	Scalable distribution of confidential workloads is important for complex 6G systems to be efficient and sustainable.	Orchestration system available.
WP4_NF_1	Interoperability, Scalability	Confidential workloads SHOULD be distributable to constrained edge devices and cloud platforms.	Compatibility assures that confidential computing workloads can be deployed to infrastructure from different vendors. The requirement facilitates scalability.	Orchestration of confidential code demonstrated to several platforms integrated.
WP4_NF_1 2	Interoperability	Confidential software SHOULD be seamlessly usable on different confidential computing platforms.	Use of standard approaches for orchestrating confidential workloads improves portability and flexibility.	Seamless orchestration of confidential code demonstrated to several platforms.
WP4_NF_1 3	Interoperability	The system MUST be compatible with various	To ensure accessibility and usability across	The system operates on Windows, macOS,

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

		operating systems and devices.	different environments.	Linux, iOS, and Android platforms.
WP4_NF_1 4	Ethics, societal, management	Distributed confidential AI components SHOULD be securely accessible, monitorable and configurable.	EU Artificial Intelligence Act requires human oversight, i.e., human-machine interfaces enabling high-risk AI systems to be overseen by natural persons	Secure control channel in for remote confidential workloads possible to realize (e.g. part of orchestration system)

4 USE CASE REQUIREMENTS

The project has initially identified three different use cases (UC1, UC2, and UC3) that will be used to validate the developed components. The use cases will be further developed in WP5. Because these use case descriptions describe intended use of the components, those descriptions are also a good source of requirements.

4.1 USE CASE 1: PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE FOR AIRLINE CONSORTIUM

This use-case implements a platform for secure and trackable data sharing between aviation companies, manufacturers, regulation bodies and other organizations. The main goal is to enable predictive maintenance, driven by AI/ML, on top of shared data. Aviation companies dispose huge amounts of valuable data however algorithms trained on data sets collected by a single company are not precise enough due to the fact that each individual company has a limited number of certain types of aeroplane in their fleet. Hence, data is very valuable, but companies with competing interests are not willing to share their data easily. The aim of this use case is to showcase how privacy-preserving computation and secure data sharing via blockchain could help to overcome the aforementioned challenges. Technologies that will be utilised include blockchain networks with confidential Smart Contracts and Fully Homomorphic Encryption to enable private transactions that log data exchange. Further, federated AI/ML will be applied in order for confidential containers carrying algorithms to be transported over Kubernetes clusters to the edge data centres that are placed near the airports. This is done not only because data is private and it should not leave the premise, but also because in this particular case data is huge, and time for algorithm application is often very short (between two flights), so in many cases it is even not possible to move data centrally. Finally - FHE and SMPC will be applied to ensure that data set from each organisation stays encrypted while the algorithm is applied.

Key KPIs include the increase in trustworthiness of container orchestration for multi-party computation and increase in efficiency with federated AI/ML for large consortiums and large data sets.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

4.1.1 REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

4.1.1.1 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 6: Functional Requirements of Predictive Maintenance for Airline Consortium Using Blockchain-based Data Sharing Platform and Federated AI/ML Orchestration (UC1)

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP4_UC1_F R_1	Data Reliability	The system MUST ensure reliable data for predictive maintenance by using ML and blockchain to validate, filter, and store accurate and tamper-proof data.	Avoids faulty predictions, ensures operational efficiency, and maintains trust in data integrity.	95% of data is verified as reliable and stored with 100% integrity.
WP4_UC1_F R_2	Networking	The system MUST utilize confidential containers with Kubernetes support for edge computing.	To ensure secure execution of AI/ML algorithms at the edge.	AI/ML algorithms run in confidential containers with no unauthorized access detected.
WP4_UC1_F R_3	Networking	The system MUST implement post-quantum TLS for network communication.	To protect data against quantum computing threats.	All network communications are encrypted using post-quantum TLS and verified through security audits.
WP4_UC1_F R_4	AI/ML Orchestration	The system MUST support federated AI/ML orchestration for predictive maintenance algorithms.	To enable collaborative AI/ML model training without sharing raw data.	Federated AI/ML models are successfully trained and deployed with performance metrics meeting predefined KPIs.
WP4_UC1_F R_5	Security	All system components, participating nodes and users MUST be	Implementation of Authentication and Authorisation.	Authentication works properly. Authorization

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

		authenticated and authorized with assigned access rights based on their role.		works based on defined roles and access control policies.
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4.1.1.2 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 7: Non-functional Requirements of Predictive Maintenance for Airline Consortium Using Blockchain-based Data Sharing Platform and Federated AI/ML Orchestration (UC1)

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP4_UC1_NF_1	Interoperability	The system SHOULD be compatible with existing airline maintenance systems.	To ensure seamless integration and data exchange with current systems.	Compatibility MUST be verified through integration testing with different airline maintenance systems.
WP4_UC1_NF_2	Interoperability	The system MUST be compatible with existing network protocols and infrastructure used by the airline consortium, including integration with multiparty computation and post-quantum TLS.	To ensure seamless integration with current systems and avoid the need for extensive modifications.	Integration tests confirm compatibility with existing network protocols and infrastructure.
WP4_UC1_NF_3	Regulatory	The use case system SHOULD be aligned with global	Compliance with global regulations, such as the General Data	Keep ethical and legal compliance in consideration during all stages. Adoption of

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

		<p>regulations, such as GDPR, ensuring sensitive data (e.g., maintenance logs) is protected.</p>	<p>Protection Regulation (GDPR), is essential for systems handling sensitive data. Aligning the system with such regulations builds trust among stakeholders, including airlines, manufacturers, and maintenance providers. It also mitigates the risk of legal penalties, reputational damage, and operational disruptions resulting from non-compliance. Moreover, adherence to international data protection standards ensures interoperability and smooth collaboration across regions with different legal frameworks.</p>	<p>adequate technical and organisational measures as per the Data Management Plan, minimization and anonymization of all data to the extent possible.</p>
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4.2 USE CASE 2: PRIVACY-PRESERVING CONFIDENTIAL COMPUTING PLATFORM

This use-case will provide enablement for confidential computing in the form of a defined platform that can be applied in the telecom clouds. A current problem with confidential computing is that in many cases it depends on new hardware

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

architectures - notably Intel's Intel Trust Domain Extensions (TDX) and AMD's SEV. Industry is moving towards Virtual Machine (VM)-based TEEs, but their enablement is still in the early phases. Open-source projects - like RedHat's Enarx¹ and ARM's Veracruz² - are working on the subject but have approaches that need more research. Use of Confidential containers is also an option since containers provide generalization and the infrastructure for orchestration of container-based applications already exists.

4.2.1 REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

4.2.1.1 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 8: Functional Requirements of Privacy-preserving Confidential Computing Platform (UC2)

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP4_UC2_FR_1	Networking	Networking MUST be enabled on the host machine to support networking from TEEs.	Network communication with TEE.	The networking is enabled on the host.
WP4_UC2_FR_2	Networking, Security, Trust	The whole TLS stack SHOULD be in the TEE.	Network communication between the end-user and the TEE.	The whole TLS stack is inside the TEE.
WP4_UC2_FR_3	Networking, Security	The TLS version 1.3 or later MUST be used for communication between the end-user and the TEE.	Secure communication between the TEE and end-user.	The TLS version 1.3 is used.

¹ <https://enarx.dev/>

² <https://veracruz-project.com/>

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

WP4_UC2_FR_4	Networking, Security	The attestation MUST be an integral part of TLS connection.	Verification and validation of the TEE.	The attestation is part of the TLS connection and the TEE is verified and validated.
WP4_UC2_FR_5	Networking, Management	The firewall rules MUST be set in such a way that the end-user can communicate with the TEE.	Network communication between the end-user and the TEE.	The firewall rules are set.
WP4_UC2_FR_6	Networking, Security	Client pre-shared public key MUST be available inside the TEE.	Mutual TLS.	Mutual TLS is enabled.
WP4_UC2_FR_7	Security, Trust	The policies for verification and validation of the TEE MUST be provided to the end-user by the owner of the TEE or a trusted source.	Verification and validation of the attestation report in attested TLS.	The policy is implemented and can be obtained from the TEE hardware owner.

4.2.1.2 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 9: Non-functional Requirements of Privacy-preserving Confidential Computing Platform (UC2)

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP4_UC2_NF_1	Networking, Platform	Users MUST be able to access TEE directly using secure channels. Using direct access prevents using cloud platforms as middleware.	Connection between the user and the TEE.	TLS is used.
WP4_UC2_NF_2	Networking, Platform	All the networking protection methods in UC2 SHOULD be updated regularly to provide as strong and	Regular security updates.	30% done.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

		up-to-date protection as possible.		
WP4_UC2_NF_3	Data, Privacy	All the data access and storage requirements for UC2 MUST be compliant with regulations for data protection, both general and AI-specific.	Regulatory requirement.	30% done.
WP4_UC2_NF_4	Scalability, Performance	The system SHOULD be able to handle concurrent TLS sessions.	Multiple users want to connect to the same TEE.	The TEE can handle multiple connections.
WP4_UC2_NF_5	Security, Data	Sensitive data MUST be used only inside the TEE.	Using sensitive data.	The data is only used inside the TEE.
WP4_UC2_NF_6	Security	TLS connections MUST be maintained and if they fail they MUST be properly cleaned up and terminated.	Connection between the user and the TEE.	The TLS stack is inside the TEE and is terminated when the TEE is destroyed.
WP4_UC2_NF_7	Security	Users SHOULD be able to define their policies for verification and validation of attestation when using attested TLS.	Connection between the user and the TEE.	The user can modify the policy used for verification and validation.

4.3 USE CASE 3: INTELLIGENT CONNECTED VEHICLES

This use case will provide mission-critical services in the context of secure Vehicle to Infrastructure (V2I) communications, and over-the-air (OTA) vehicle system updates, with distributed learning. The use case will be simulated using data from

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

car modules, with Subscriber Identity Module (SIM) 4G/5G interface. Data from a number of vehicles will be used to perform AI/ML based on the data shared among the vehicles and the roadside infrastructures. In this case, distributed Learning and data sharing will provide great benefits to enhance road safety and driving experiences by supporting driving decision making.

The goal is given to the evaluation of the effectiveness of the proposed technology for security in future connected car scenarios. Further to this, Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEMs) and car manufacturers can provide the ability to train their own sensing or driving data by the on-board computing devices, and obtain corresponding parameters (e.g., models/policies) as refined knowledge. Various levels of knowledge (such as traffic statistics, traffic control, driving rules, sensing, and driving models) would be possible to share among the vehicles and the roadside infrastructures. Data on connected vehicles will be used to emulate FL and ML problems related to network connectivity 5G/6G.

4.3.1 REQUIREMENTS ANALYSIS

4.3.1.1 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 10: Functional Requirements of Intelligent Connected Vehicles (UC3)

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP4_UC3_FR_1	Security	Update process MUST ensure the authenticity and integrity of the software updates during transfer.	Provide OTA updates based on VC.	Authentication and integration of the software updates during transfer.
WP4_UC3_FR_2	Blockchain	Use of blockchain for protecting sensitive data and SW update immutability. The system MUST employ blockchain to protect sensitive data from manipulation and guarantee the immutability of	Provide data fabric for firmware updates.	Blockchain-based protection for sensitive data and software update immutability, enabling integrity verification through stored hashes.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

		<p>software updates. Hashes of software updates must be stored on the blockchain, and vehicles should be able to verify the integrity of received updates using blockchain records.</p>		
WP4_UC3_FR_3	Identity Management	<p>Each connected car MUST have a digital identity that allows verification of which cars require updates, and which have already been updated. Vehicles should possess a credential certifying the successful installation of updates (e.g., V2I VC to semi disclosing information).</p>	Develop Vehicle digital identity for update verification.	Digital identity management for connected cars to verify update status and certify successful installations.
WP4_UC3_FR_4	Privacy, Security	<p>The system MUST assess and implement secured and privacy-preserving communication methods for FL server interactions. Protection mechanisms, for example based on DP, MUST be in place to guard against different privacy FL attacks, like attribute, property, or</p>	Protections for protection against privacy FL attacks.	Implementation of secure and privacy-preserving communication protocols for federated learning, incorporating protection mechanisms against privacy attacks.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

		membership inference attacks.		
WP4_UC3_FR_5	Security	The system MUST include mechanisms to make the FL models resistant to faulty updates and capable of mitigating data or model poisoning attacks.	Protections for protection against faulty updates and poisoning attacks.	Development of robust mechanisms to enhance federated learning model resilience against faulty updates and data/model poisoning attacks.
WP4_UC3_FR_6	Data Processing	Because the data sending frequency is high, the model MUST be able to make the necessary preprocessing accurately and quickly.	Efficient pre-processing	Development of efficient pre-processing techniques for rapid and accurate data handling in high-frequency environments.
WP4_UC3_FR_7	Federated Learning	Implement algorithms for enhancing the fairness of the FL models, so that the performance of the predictions across different sets of vehicles SHOULD be similar.	Fair FL models	Development of algorithms to ensure fairness in federated learning models, promoting consistent prediction performance across diverse vehicle sets.
WP4_UC3_FR_8	Federated Learning	Given the connectivity of vehicles in this scenario, the aggregator MUST be able to perform model updates asynchronously, as some of the participants may not	Asynchronous aggregation of the FL model.	Implementation of asynchronous aggregation techniques for federated learning models to accommodate variable connectivity among vehicles.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

		be connected or have relevant updates for the model.		
WP4_UC3_FR_9	Security	The system MUST support post-quantum TLS to ensure secure communication and encryption for off-chain data, resistant to potential quantum computing attacks.	Post-quantum TLS provides enhanced security by utilizing encryption techniques that are resistant to quantum computing threats, ensuring long-term data protection during communication.	The system implements post-quantum TLS protocols for all off-chain data exchanges, ensuring secure encryption methods that remain effective against future quantum computing capabilities.
WP4_UC3_FR_10	Data Management	The system SHOULD create backup and recovery procedures to prevent data loss and facilitate system restoration in case of failures.	Data Backup and Recovery	Development of backup and recovery protocols to ensure data integrity and system restoration.
WP4_UC3_FR_11	Identity Management	The SSI Bridge MUST perform efficiently for issuing and revoking VC for vehicles.	SSI Bridge Performance	Optimization of the SSI Bridge for efficient issuance and revocation of vehicle credentials.
WP4_UC3_FR_12	Access Control	Authorization processes SHOULD be based on VC to provide secure access control.	Authorization and Access Control	Implementation of authorization processes utilizing verifiable credentials (VC) for enhanced access control.
WP4_UC3_FR_13	Privacy	The system MUST protect data privacy while ensuring secure	Reduces risks of privacy leakage and unauthorized access during data	No privacy leakages detected in data-sharing processes.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

		sharing in the FL process.	exchange in connected vehicles.	
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4.3.1.2 NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Table 11: Non-functional Requirements of Intelligent Connected Vehicles (UC3)

ID	Category	Description	Rationale	Fit Criterion
WP4_UC3_NF_1	Performance	The system SHOULD satisfy acceptable response times for various system operations, such as credential issuance and AI/ML processing.	Performance Requirements	Establishment of acceptable response time benchmarks for system operations including credential issuance.
WP4_UC3_NF_2	Blockchain	The blockchain SHOULD support timestamping and versioning of ADL models to track changes and maintain integrity.	Develop blockchain-based tamper proofing of ADL models.	Blockchain implementation for tamper-proofing ADL models with support for timestamping and versioning.
WP4_UC3_NF_3	Federated Learning	Since the conditions of the vehicles (and the installed devices) are constantly changing, the models MUST be able to adapt to new conditions and domain changes.	Continuous training of the FL models.	Implementation of continuous training mechanisms for federated learning models to adapt to evolving vehicle conditions.
WP4_UC3_NF_4	System Reliability	The system SHOULD allow the specification of the	System Uptime	Definition of system availability and

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

		required system availability and reliability constraints, considering critical use cases such as OTA updates and data processing.		reliability requirements for critical operations like OTA updates.
WP4_UC3_NF_5	Privacy, Security	The system MUST maintain the privacy and anonymity of users when handling anonymous credentials and decentralized identities.	End user Privacy Techniques must be implemented that anonymize any personally identifiable information in vehicle data.	Establishment of privacy-preserving mechanisms to protect user anonymity in the management of anonymous credentials and decentralized identities.
WP4_UC3_NF_6	Security	The system SHALL be resilient against faulty model updates and data/model poisoning attacks during federated learning.	Safeguarding the integrity of FL models is crucial to preventing malicious interference.	Robust detection and mitigation strategies are employed to counteract faulty updates and model poisoning.
WP4_UC3_NF_7	Scalability, Performance	The system SHALL be adaptive to new conditions, enabling continuous updates of FL models to handle evolving vehicle environments.	As vehicles encounter dynamic environments, the system must update and adapt FL models without frequent retraining.	Continuous model adaptation techniques are integrated to adjust to domain and environmental changes.
WP4_UC3_NF_8	Data Processing	The system SHALL be efficient in processing high-frequency data by	Efficient data handling ensures smooth operation in	Preprocessing techniques are applied to handle incoming

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

		quickly and accurately filtering and transforming it for use in federated learning models.	high-volume data environments.	data rapidly and accurately before model training.
WP4_UC3_NF_9	Regulatory	The use case system SHOULD be aligned with global regulations, such as GDPR, ensuring sensitive data (e.g., maintenance logs) is protected.	Compliance with global regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), is essential for systems handling sensitive data. Aligning the system with such regulations builds trust among stakeholders, including airlines, manufacturers, and maintenance providers. It also mitigates the risk of legal penalties, reputational damage, and operational disruptions resulting from non-compliance. Moreover, adherence to international data protection standards ensures interoperability and smooth collaboration across regions with different legal frameworks.	Keep ethical and legal compliance in consideration during all stages. Adoption of adequate technical and organizational measures as per the Data Management Plan, minimization and anonymization of all data to the extent possible.

5 ARCHITECTURE BLUEPRINTS

5.1 HIGH LEVEL ARCHITECTURE

Confidential networking guarantees secure data exchange and sharing over the cloud-edge communication, control and orchestration infrastructure in 6G networks. It improves data privacy in applications like FL, Internet of Vehicles and distributed data sharing. A high-level architecture for secure and confidential

networking can be found in **Figure 2**.

Figure 2: High Level Architecture for Secure and Confidential Networking

Generally, to enable confidential networking based on requirements presented in Section 2 and 3, the following mechanisms/components are important:

- **Confidential orchestration:** orchestration mechanism that allows deployment and configuration of applications, algorithms, and data to

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

different computing platforms for execution in a manner that the application is kept isolated and confidential from the platform provider.

- **Data sharing mechanism** that allows secure and decentralized data exchange and sharing while ensuring its confidentiality, integrity and traceability.
- **Secure decentralized data sharing** that enhances federated AI/ML privacy-preservation in 6G networks.
- **Long term security mechanism** especially quantum safe communication that protects 6G communication system against quantum attackers.

The implementation of these mechanisms relies both on all kinds of cryptographic techniques and tools, including both software and hardware. The detailed design will depend on the specific application and may require a combination of techniques to achieve the desired level of security.

- **Software:** SMC, HE, FL, PQC primitives, DLT, ZKP
- **Hardware:** TEEs, FPGA

Based on these cryptographic techniques, the following section will present you a comprehensive guidance on the components designed for secure and confidential networking in 6G:

- Confidential orchestration based on confidential containers
- Secure and traceable data sharing based on DLT
- Federated AI/ML orchestration based on DP, TEEs
- Quantum safe communication based on post-quantum TLS and other networking protocols.

5.2 CONFIDENTIAL ORCHESTRATION

Orchestration is the coordination and management of computer systems, applications and/or services, stringing together multiple tasks to execute workflows or processes. Orchestration means deployment and configuration of applications and services over network to cloud, edge, and device platforms. Confidential orchestration refers to deployment and configuration of applications, algorithms, and data to different computing platforms for execution in a manner that the application is kept isolated and confidential from the platform provider.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

The architecture adopts the concept of containers as units that can be orchestrated over the network. Container is a standard package of software that contains application code and dependencies. It is a lightweight virtualization approach that can be used to deploy code quickly to different platforms. The goal of the architecture is to enable orchestration and confidentiality-protection of containers even when they are deployed to platforms that are not completely trusted. A prominent container system is Docker. Solutions have also emerged for automating the deployments, configuration, and scaling of the containers. These container orchestrations systems include Kubernetes. The architecture introduces two new types of containers: encrypted container is a container that is secured using cryptographic means and hardware-secure container is a container that is secured with TEEs.

Figure 3: Initial Architectural Consideration of Components Relevant for Confidential Orchestration

The orchestration architecture in Figure 3 highlights the main components that we have identified as essential for orchestrating algorithms and data from the client (i.e., the owner of confidential asset) to service provider domain that is not completely trusted. The trust model is highlighted with a trust boundary (dashed line) in the **Figure 3**. In the high-level, the confidentiality of deployment can be

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

based either on security hardware (here trusted containers and illustrated with light blue) or on cryptographic means (here encrypted containers and illustrated with dark blue). The separation of the basis of trust (encrypted vs. trusted containers) is illustrated with the dotted line.

The architecture is based on the following components and enablers:

- Container orchestration system – Is a platform for automating deployment, scaling, and management of containerized applications. For instance, Kubernetes is a prominent open-source implementation of orchestration system.
- Trusted containers – The hardware-secured containers will leverage available TEEs, which are integrated to container orchestration solutions, to isolate them from the host platform and other distrusted containers. A prominent trusted container open-source solution is Confidential Containers (CoCo) project.
- Encrypted containers – Software-based applications can be secured using advanced cryptographic means such as fully homomorphic cryptography.
- Orchestration intelligence – Applications can be orchestrated on different cloud, edge, and device platforms. Orchestration intelligence deploys and configures containerized applications based on application provider's needs and on available information, e.g., of host platform's capability or security health.
- Remote attestation – Application provider can verify trustworthiness of target host and containerization systems before critical containers are deployed. Remote attestation is a method where a host authenticates its hardware and software configuration to a remote party (provider).
- Secure control channel – Deployment and configuration of containers requires secure services and secure communication between provider and host. Secure communication may also be required for different confidential containers.

5.3 DLT-BASED DATA SHARING

Secure and traceable data sharing involves sharing sensitive information while ensuring its confidentiality, integrity, and accountability.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

- **Confidentiality:** Only authorized individuals or entities should be able to access the shared data. This is achieved through encryption and other security measures.
- **Integrity:** The data cannot be tampered with or altered during the sharing process. This is often achieved through digital signatures and other cryptographic techniques.
- **Accountability:** It is possible to track who accessed the data and when. This is achieved through logging and auditing mechanisms.

Traceability allows for:

- **Transparency:** The data owner knows who has accessed their data and what they did with it.
- **Auditing:** The data owner can verify that the data has been handled appropriately.
- **Compliance:** The data owner can comply with regulations that require data to be traceable.
- **Attribution:** The data owner can attribute any misuse of the data to the responsible party.

The increasing deployment of edge computing devices creates a need for secure and traceable data sharing mechanisms. Blockchain technology, with its inherent security and immutability features, offers a promising solution for addressing these concerns. Additionally, confidential networking technologies like TEEs can further enhance data privacy and confidentiality.

Figure 4 depicts the architecture blueprint for secure and traceable data sharing.

Figure 4: Secure and Traceable Data Sharing based on DLT

A description of each component is provided in the following:

Edge Layer

- Edge Devices: Collect and preprocess data from sensors, cameras, and other sources.
- Confidential Data Store: Securely store sensitive data on the edge device using encryption and access control mechanisms.
- Data Preprocessing Module: Preprocess data to protect privacy and reduce bandwidth consumption.

Confidential Networking Layer

- Private Network: Dedicated network for confidential data communication between edge devices and trusted parties.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

- Confidential Networking: Utilize TEEs on edge devices and network nodes for secure data processing and in-network aggregation.
- Confidential Computing: Employ cryptographic protocols like HE and secure MPC to enable secure data analysis without compromising confidentiality.

Secure Data Sharing and Access Control

- Blockchain Platform: Distributed ledger technology for immutably recording and tracing data transactions.
- Smart Contracts: Automate data sharing agreements, access control, and data usage policies.
- Data Integrity and Provenance: Verify the authenticity and origin of data using blockchain's tamper-proof features.

Application Layer

- Control access to data based on pre-defined policies and permissions.
- Perform data analysis while preserving the privacy of individual data contributors.
- Enable secure and transparent data sharing for various applications and services.
- Visualization

Tools

- Blockchain platforms: Ethereum, Hyperledger Fabric, etc.
- Data Sharing Platform: Nokia Data Exchange
- Confidential networking solutions: Intel SGX, AMD SEV, etc.
- Secure communication libraries: OpenSSL, libsodium, etc.
- Data privacy tools: DP, FL, etc.

Data Flow

1. Data Collection: Edge devices collect data from various sources.
2. Data Preprocessing: Sensitive data is pre-processed on the edge device to protect privacy and reduce bandwidth consumption.
3. Data Transfer: Pre-processed data is transferred securely through the private network utilizing confidential networking technologies.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

4. Data Storage: Data is securely stored in the confidential data store on the edge device.
5. Data Sharing: Data sharing requests are initiated through the application layer and authorized by smart contracts on the blockchain.
6. Data Access: Authorized users access data through secure channels and privacy-preserving data analytics techniques.

5.4 FEDERATED AI/ML

5.4.1 FL COMPUTING

A FL component in a system architecture generally refers to a module or a set of functionalities designed to facilitate decentralized ML. This component operates under the principles of FL, where a model is trained across multiple decentralized edge devices or servers holding local data samples, without exchanging them. **Error! Reference source not found.** is a generic description for such a component.

Figure 5: Overview of FL Computing

The FL component is a crucial segment of the system architecture dedicated to enabling collaborative ML while preserving data privacy and security. This component is architecturally designed to handle decentralized data sources, where the learning process is distributed across multiple nodes.

The key features of this building block are as follows:

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

- **Data Localization:** The component ensures that data remains on its original device, thereby maintaining privacy and adhering to data protection regulations.
- **Model Training and Aggregation:** It facilitates the training of local models on edge devices or nodes. These local models are then aggregated into a global model, which iteratively improves with each training round.
- **Communication Efficiency:** The component is optimized for efficient communication, ensuring minimal data transfer to reduce network load and latency. This involves sending only essential model updates, rather than the entire data or model.
- **Security and Privacy:** Incorporates advanced security protocols to protect the models and the training process. This includes encryption techniques and possibly DP measures to prevent data leakage.
- **Scalability and Flexibility:** Designed to be scalable to handle numerous nodes and flexible to accommodate various types of data and learning models.

The main components of this framework are nodes and server.

Figure 6: Server Diagram in FL Computing

Server can be found in **Figure 6**:

- Contains the users, organizations, collaborations, tasks and their results.
- Authentication and authorization for clients and nodes
- Entities such as tasks, users, and nodes can be managed through a RESTful Application Programming Interface (API), and a WebSocket channel allows

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

for communication of simple messages between components, reducing server requests and improving efficiency.

- The server can host a private registry of Docker images and corresponding RESTful API, which are delivered to the nodes for execution.
- Data processor can also upload their own Docker images, but all images must be approved by the involved nodes to ensure autonomy in data access.

Figure 7: Party Node Diagram in FL Computing

Node can be found in **Figure 7**.

- Node only transmits to the server a set of aggregated values (i.e., coefficients)
- The node receives a task from the server, downloads a Docker image, accesses local data, and executes the algorithm with given parameters.
- The algorithm outputs intermediate results, which are sent to the server through a RESTful API and can be iteratively computed until the global solution converges.
- Data always stays at the original location, only intermediate results are transmitted, and all messages are end-to-end encrypted for added security.
- Heterogeneous parties can host nodes if they comply with minimal system requirements.

5.4.2 FL ORCHESTRATION

For FL orchestration we will be using as a reference the architecture of Federated Learning as a Service (FLaaS) proposed by TID in [4] and [5]. This architecture is more oriented for training of FL models in cross device settings, which is relevant

for the settings in the use cases in WP5 and is aimed to offer collaborative training of ML models in an “as a learning fashion”. For this, FLaaS addresses the following design challenges:

- **Easy to use:** It needs to provide a simple interface for setting up the FL training process and to be incorporated in different apps easily.
- **Multi use case coverage:** FLaaS considers single and cross-app modelling scenarios. Thus, several applications in the same device can collaborate for training a FL model.
- **On device training** enabling background ML training.
- **Secure and private training:** 1) FLaaS enables a secure communication channel between apps; 2) Secure data and model storage; 3) Secure authentication and communication between the FLaaS back-end and the client devices (achieved via authentication tokens and encrypted communication mechanisms). FLaaS also supports the incorporation of robust aggregation techniques, DP, and its integrations with TEEs.
- **Easy to deploy:** FLaaS needs to be deployed in different environments and needs to deal with production challenges like scalability or robustness.

Figure 8: FLaaS High Level Overview in [4]

As shown in **Figure 8**, in FLaaS, a set of K devices with N installed apps securely share their local datasets or locally trained models with the local service. Then, they are aggregated locally to produce a local model. The model parameters from all K devices are securely aggregated using some aggregation algorithm (e.g., Federated Averaging [6]) as in most FL approaches. Note that, at each training round, a subset of the devices may be selected to provide model updates to the aggregator, i.e., not all devices are required to participate at each training round.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

In **Figure 9**, we show the different components of the FLaaS architecture: The set of clients participating in the FL task through the FLaaS infrastructure, periodically report their status through the back-end's REST API (1) to the DB for logging (2). An APP developer can use the Admin Interface to create a new FLaaS project (3), whose configuration is stored in the DB (4). Once the new FLaaS project is created, the Device Scheduler detects it (5), queries the status of the devices from the DB (5), and then, sends a request for training the FL model using its Notification Service Provider (6a) to external services (e.g., APN and FCM) (6b). When each device receives the FL training request (7) and requests from the participating third-party apps to receive either their local data points for training, or to train their own models (8a) - (8c), the device performs the necessary model training steps (on-device) or model aggregation and averaging, depending on the training mode. Finally, when a substantial number of reported models is received by the Server (1), the Device Scheduler asks the Model Aggregator to aggregate the received models (9a and 9b), marking the FL round as complete, and continuing with the next round of FL training. The process is repeated until some stopping requirements are reached (e.g., maximum number of training rounds).

Figure 9: FLaaS Architecture in [4]

One of the main benefits of this architecture is that it can work in scenarios with heterogeneous devices and with flexible configurations, allowing for example, cross-app collaboration for training FL models. This architecture also provides flexibility to use different types of robust aggregation and privacy techniques to mitigate vulnerabilities to poisoning and privacy attacks. On the other hand, FLaaS can be used in combination with TEEs, as shown in [7], which can help to provide solutions for stricter privacy and security requirements. Thus, FLaaS provides a

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

reasonable architecture to support the work and contributions on FL to be investigated and developed in WP4 and validated in the use cases in WP5.

5.4.3 FEDERATED LEARNING SECURITY/ PRIVACY

5.4.3.1 FL DEFENSE AGAINST POISONOUS ATTACKS WITH BLOCKCHAIN

FL has become the next generation of ML by avoiding local data sharing with a central server. While this becomes a major advantage to client-side privacy, it has a trade-off of becoming vulnerable to poisoning attacks and malicious behaviour of the central server. As the decentralization of systems enhances security concerns, integrating decentralized defence for the existing FL systems has been extensively studied to eliminate the security issues of FL systems. This directive proposes a decentralized defence approach to FL systems with blockchain technology to overcome the poisoning attack without affecting the existing FL system's performance. Thus, Figure 10 illustrates a reliable blockchain-based FL architecture in two different models, namely, Centralized Aggregated Blockchain Federated Learning (CA-BCFL) and Fully Decentralized Blockchain Federated Learning (FD-BCFL). Both models utilize secure off-chain computations for malicious mitigation as an alternative to high-cost on-chain computations. With this approach, we intend to reinforce the defences of FL systems against poisonous attempts.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

Figure 10: Blockchain based Poisoning Defence Strategy for FL

5.4.3.2 FL DEFENSE AGAINST POISONOUS ATTACKS WITH EXPLAINABLE AI

State-of-the-art relating to the FL poisonous threats still needs a holistic solution that can defend against such attacks with FL-network awareness. This awareness can be gained through a standardized framework that can reveal the statistics of the FL model updates without compromising its privacy. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) is a concept that can be followed globally for regulating policies and standards and has the potential to achieve this objective. Thus, for a well-designed FL poisoning defence mechanism engaging XAI should entail addressing the following open issues:

1. What is the probable threat landscape for poisoning attacks in an FL convergence network?
2. Which FL model parameters are subjected to poisoning threats?
3. How would poisonous attacks impact the influential instances of a local FL model?
4. How to extend the influence function to encode the XAI influential instances, so that the privacy of the local data is preserved?

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

5. How to detect poisonous threats utilizing the defined XAI influence parameters?

Under this directive of T4.4, we are proposing a solution for the obvious poisoning threats enforced on the FL models. As the state-of-the-art analysis entails, XAI is not a concept that has been visualized as a solution for this security issue in FL. Our keen insight suggests that XAI can be standardized to a level for mitigating or defending against poisoning threats through early and active detection of malicious FL nodes. Thus, Figure 11 illustrates the tentative methodology to accomplish the goals defined within this task.

Figure 11: Overview of the XAI-enabled FL Poisoning Defence Strategy

The main outcome of this task is a detection mechanism of poisonous attempts employing the XAI interpretable parameters. These parameters will not only enable the detection of security threats but provide a reflection on the performance metrics of the overall FL process. Thus, a trade-off of defence mechanisms against the convergence of the FL process can be evaluated at the concluding stages. The main objectives of this task can be listed below:

1. Identifying the threat landscape of possible poisoning attempts on FL systems.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

2. Identifying the influential instances of the FL process that are impacted by the poisonous attacks.
3. Develop a mechanism to share the identified influential parameters without compromising the privacy of the FL local data.
4. Develop and validate an FL poisonous detection mechanism employing the identified XAI parameters.

5.4.3.3 SECURITY TESTING/VERIFICATION ARCHITECTURE

Figure 12: FL Security Testbed

As illustrated in **Figure 12**, UCD already possesses an active 5G test network within its premises. The current network is comprehensively extended from the core network to the IoT end devices. The OAIBOX³, Cumucore⁴, and the DenseAir⁵ Core network servers are linked with the system from the core network point of view. In

³ <https://oaibox.com/>

⁴ <https://cumucore.com/>

⁵ <https://denseair.net/>

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

fact, these are the pioneers in leading the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) concept through their developments. Three core network servers are connected to the RAN devices that are interfaced through the PowerEdge R7515 edge server launched as the controller for the IoT side. We followed the Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) edge computing infrastructure defined under 3GPP Rel. 17. In the initial setup, the intention was to launch an autonomous service infrastructure at the edge that acts as an intermediary central aggregator for the learning models. The edge server is linked to several Nvidia Jetson AGX Orin devices, which are capable of operating as FL nodes for different FL clusters individually. Several IoT networks are formed with Raspberry Pi4 and Nvidia Jetson nano System on Chips (SoCs) which act as aggregators of actuator devices or IoT network hubs. IoT networks are built around typical household appliances, e-health wearables, and atmospheric actuators. The wireless communication between the devices leading up to the FL nodes is established via HackRF One Software Defined Radio (SDR) devices or Wi-Fi connectivity. This test network architecture will be utilized for running the intended verification/validation experiments regarding all the FL constructs under Task 4.4.

5.5 POST-QUANTUM TLS

TLS is arguably the most important security protocol on the Internet. Using it two parties can authenticate each other and securely exchange messages over insecure networks. TLS generally implements end-to-end security. In 5G, TLS is mostly used to protect data transmission in the core network. This is likely to continue in 6G as well. Unfortunately, the most recent TLS protocol is not secure against quantum computers. For long-term security we thus need to rely on a new protocol in 6G. In this section we will describe the architecture of a post-quantum secure security protocol. The architecture will be very close to TLS except for the mathematical parts that should ensure post-quantum security.

Figure 13: Post-quantum TLS Security Protocol Design

Underlying all communication in 6G, there must be a reliable security mechanism to securely exchange data between two parties. In the core network, this can be realized by a security protocol, which works as a post-quantum secure variant of the widespread TLS protocol. In general, we must consider 4 modules. The first three are part of the so-called handshake phase. The last one represents the secure connection phase. Cryptographic protocols in general should consider two use cases:

- **Client-Server setting:** we have an asymmetric setup. Clients request a connection from the server. Moreover, clients do not need to have cryptographic authentication material present (anonymous clients) although they can. Often clients are much more lightweight and only support a restricted set of algorithms that they can use. Servers on the other hand typically have much more resources than clients and can support a variety of cryptographic algorithms.
- **Balanced setting:** it features a symmetric setup. Here parties have similar capabilities and in general they run the protocol with mutual authentication where both parties have cryptographic credentials (certificates) for authentication. In TLS this use case is referred to as mTLS (mutual TLS).

Phase 1: The ciphersuite negotiation phase is the first crucial step in the protocol run. It represents an initial communication between the two communication parties.

During this phase, the parties agree on a set of cryptographic algorithms and parameters that are used to secure the rest of the communication with. This must consider what each party can do. In the Client-Server setting, clients may be severely restricted. We recommend defining a set of default algorithms. Each client must implement at least one of these algorithms. Servers, however, must implement all of them. This guarantees that clients can always communicate with servers.

Phase 2: The certificate verification phase is an optional phase. It is not needed in case key material is pre-distributed among the parties, for example if parties use pre-distributed symmetric keys or pre-distributed public keys. In all other cases it is a complex and crucial step in the handshake process where the client verifies the authenticity of the server's public key based on a trust hierarchy. Traditionally, it relies on classically secure digital signatures. Our new protocol will rely on post-quantum secure digital signatures. This phase is essential for ensuring the integrity of the communication and establishing trust between the client and server. Here is an overview of the certificate verification phase:

- **Certificate Transmission:** As part of the protocol handshake, the server sends its digital certificate to the client.
- **Certificate Content:** The digital certificate contains the server's public key and information about the server, including the server's identity and the digital signature of the certificate authority that issued the certificate.
- **Certificate Authority Verification:** The client needs to verify the authenticity of the server's certificate. This involves checking whether the digital signature on the certificate is valid and whether the certificate has been issued by a trusted Certificate Authority.
- **Chain of Trust:** The client checks the entire chain of trust, ensuring that each certificate in the chain is signed by the issuing certificate authority. The root certificate authority's certificate is typically included in the client's trust store.
- **Revocation Checking:** The client may check if the server's certificate has been revoked by consulting a Certificate Revocation List or using the Online Certificate Status Protocol. This is to ensure that the certificate has not been compromised since it was issued.

D4.1 Requirements and Architecture for Confidential Networking

- **Name Verification:** The client verifies that the server's identity matches the expected identity. This is typically done by checking the Common Name or Subject Alternative Name field in the server's certificate against the hostname to which the client is trying to connect.
- **Failure Handling:** If any of the verification steps fail, the client may choose to terminate the connection or take other appropriate actions based on the security policy configured.

Phase 3: In the handshake phase, the parties run a fresh key exchange protocol that is based on freshly generated public key material. This key material is independent of the long-term keys. Traditionally, it relies on classically secure non-interactive key exchange or key encapsulation mechanism/public key encryption (KEM/PKE). In our new protocol we will rely on post-quantum secure KEMs or post-quantum secure non-interactive key exchange. The result of the key exchange is a symmetric session key k that the parties now share. The protocol additionally requires the application of the long-term secret keys of the parties to authenticate themselves. In the anonymous client setting, only the server will use its secret key, and the client will stay anonymous at this stage. The idea is that a) either the session key can only be obtained by parties that have successfully authenticated (this is called implicit authentication) or b) the parties can rely on a mechanism that explicitly recognizes unsuccessful authentication attempts by their communication partner (explicit authentication). In case b) parties can simply abort the protocol run. Both cases guarantee that session keys are only shared with authenticated parties.

Phase 4: In the final phase, the session key k is used to encrypt the actual messages that the parties want to exchange. To this end k will key a symmetric authenticated encryption system which encrypts messages while also providing integrity protection. Longer messages need to be fragmented and sent in consecutive packets.

The security protocol relies on several services provided by the system it is run on:

- **The protocol should be callable by arbitrary or specific applications on the system.** The functionality needs to be published accordingly on the system. This defines the application interface.

- **The system should allow the protocol to store cryptographic material securely and to retrieve it when needed.** Security measures should be put into place to protect access to that key material through other applications on the system. This defines the requirements of the secure storage system.
- **The protocol must have access to basic networking infrastructure (on lower abstraction levels).** This functionality must provide a way for reliable network communication, as it is provided by Transmission Control Protocol (TCP).
- **Finally, the cryptographic protocol must be able to access cryptographic algorithms on the system.** The protocol program can implement them on its own. However, since crypto algorithms have many use cases on modern systems, they will often be provided by the system as a service and implemented once and for all. In such cases the system also often provides better hardware support. Specifying how the protocol accesses the crypto algorithms defines the interface for cryptographic algorithms.

6 CONCLUSION

This deliverable collected a set of requirements and defined architectural blueprints for secure and confidential edge-cloud communication, control and orchestration infrastructure in 6G networks. It aims to serve as a reference throughout WP4 in CONFIDENTIAL6G project. Section 2 illustrated the requirements engineering and documenting template. Section 3 presented the generic requirements for secure and confidential networking. Additional requirements from the three use cases developed in WP5 are presented in Section 4. To overcome the challenges and fulfil the requirements in confidential networking, Section 5 presented a comprehensive guidance on confidential networking architecture blueprints design, which includes: confidential orchestration, DLT-base data sharing, Federated AI/ML and post-quantum TLS.

It should be noted that as work progresses the requirements and architecture for confidential networking will be updated if and as necessary in the next WP4 Deliverables.

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